

1 **The protein regulator of cytokinesis (PRC1) is a therapeutic vulnerability in lung metastasis.**

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8 PRC1 interacts with factors like NUSAP1 and ASPM in supporting spindle assembly during cytokinesis.
9 We identified activation of PRC1 in the lung metastases of humans with breast cancer. We observed
10 similar induction of PRC1 in the metastatic setting in a model of metastatic potential in lung metastatic
11 breast cancer. Tumors engage in a variety of strategies and behaviors during metastasis involving
12 proliferation, energy and the cell cycle to maximize potential of dissemination. The data point to spindle
13 and cycling-related changes in the tumor transcriptome in lung metastasis in human breast cancer and
14 identify a therapeutic targeting arena.

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16 Citations

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